

THE USE OF A RIGID BASIS AT THE STAGES OF MANUFACTURING COMPLETE REMOVABLE DENTURES

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Abstract

Due to the use of a rigid base, under adverse clinical conditions, and this is type III of the edentulous upper jaw according to Schroeder and type III-IV of the edentulous lower jaw according to Keller, the orthopedist can achieve reliable fixation and stabilization of bases with rollers in the oral cavity and prevents their displacement, deformation during the clinical stages of manufacturing complete removable laminar dentures. The above will allow you to make better dentures.

Keywords: solid base, complete removable lamellar dentures.

One of the tasks of orthopedic dentistry is the prosthetics of patients with complete edentulous. Complete removable laminar dentures are widely used in practice. These prostheses restore the disturbed form and function of the dentition, phonetics, and aesthetics. Despite a significant amount of work on the improvement of clinical and laboratory stages, the manufacture of complete removable lamellar dentures remains relevant. According to the authors, from 20 to 28% of patients who have made complete removable lamellar dentures do not use them for various reasons [1]. It is known that the significant factors influencing the effectiveness of the rehabilitation of patients with complete absence of teeth, in addition to the anatomical and topographic features of the prosthetic bed, include the quality of the clinical and laboratory stages [2], namely, the removal of a functional cast, determination and fixation of the position of the central ratio of the jaws. In the process of manufacturing complete removable lamellar dentures, a doctor or dental technician may make mistakes at these stages that will make the use of the prosthesis difficult or even impossible. Therefore, the prevention of possible errors and complications in the manufacture of complete removable lamellar dentures will make it possible to manufacture functionally effective dentures for a long time of use and reduce their negative impact on the tissues of the oral cavity. namely, when determining and fixing the central ratio of the jaw, checking the design of artificial teeth in the oral cavity.

However, there are cases when the use of traditional technology is not enough for the manufacture of functional complete removable lamellar dentures. These include: 1) pronounced atrophy of the alveolar processes, when it is almost impossible to correctly position the wax composition of the prosthesis on the prosthetic bed; 2) difficulties in determining the central ratio of the jaws (even with the use of plastic bases) in persons who have not used dentures for a long time in the absence of teeth. It is difficult to establish all the signs of the central relationship of the jaws due to the

limited time of working with wax bases without cooling; 3) patients with diseases of the musculoskeletal system, cerebral pathology, when the patient cannot fully control the conscious contraction of the masticatory muscles and accurately place the lower jaw in the position of the central ratio. To eliminate inaccuracies, we propose a two-stage method for the manufacture of complete removable lamellar dentures. The essence of the technique is as follows: first, the basis of the prosthesis (prostheses) is made according to the functional impression; the next step is the rest of the prosthesis, i.e. on the finished basis, occlusal ridges are fixed, the central ratio of the jaws is determined; followed by the placement of artificial teeth; wax is replaced by plastic. In this case, the moment of chewing loading of the finished prosthesis completely coincides with the moment of loading the base of the future prosthesis when determining the central ratio of the jaws and when checking the placement of artificial teeth, because the finished base of the prosthesis clearly takes its place on the tissues of the prosthetic bed. Complete removable lamellar dentures will be made in two stages.

The first stage:

- a) received individual spoons on models made from anatomical impressions;
- b) functional impressions were obtained under the chewing pressure of the patient and the bases of the prostheses of the upper and lower jaws were made. Bases are applied and fitted in the oral cavity.

Second phase:

- a) on the bases made and adjusted in the oral cavity, occlusal wax rollers were fixed and the central ratio of the jaws was determined by the anatomical and physiological method;
- b) the setting of artificial teeth was carried out on the bases of complete removable laminar dentures;
- c) correct placement was checked in the oral cavity;
- d) the replacement of wax with plastic was carried out according to the traditional method.

The prostheses of the upper and lower jaws were fitted and placed in the patient's mouth.

Adaptation to the prostheses was completed within two weeks, one correction was carried out. Control examination after 2 months: according to the patient, chewing with new prostheses has become much more convenient, adaptation to prostheses is complete, the function of chewing and speech is restored. Thus, in difficult clinical situations listed in the first part of the article, it is recommended to use the proposed two-stage technique for the manufacture of complete removable lamellar dentures. Only when using this technique is it possible to produce high-quality functional complete removable lamellar dentures

The purpose of the study -is to substantiate the method of using a solid base at the clinical stages of manufacturing a full-removable laminar prosthesis, in order to prevent errors at this stage. The correctness and accuracy of these stages carried out by the orthopedic dentist has a significant impact on the stabilization and balance of finished complete removable lamellar dentures [3]. in the oral cavity, since the wax base softens due to the temperature of the mouth, becomes unstable on the jaws and shifts, which forces the doctor to hold the templates with his hands. This is especially observed with pronounced atrophy of the alveolar processes. In addition, even a slight discrepancy in the height of the right and left sides of the roller or uneven pressure of the doctor's fingers on the left and right sides causes a reflex displacement of the lower jaw in the direction of greater pressure. And the need to hold the templates on the jaws with the hands of a doctor can also lead to errors [4]. Therefore, we recommend using solid bases with occlusal rollers when preparing occlusal ridges, determining the intercellular height and the central ratio of the jaws. The upper solid base with an occlusal roller with a formed prosthetic plane is fixed on the upper jaw. Next, the lower solid basis with the occlusal roller is adjusted to the upper one, without fear of displacement or decrease of the upper basis. Fitting achieve a snug fit of the entire occlusal surface of the upper and lower rollers in the anterior-posterior and transversal directions and the placement of their buccal surfaces in the same plane. The prepared lower occlusal roller on a solid basis, as well as the upper one, is fixed in the oral cavity and the interalveolar height is determined by the anatomical and physiological method [5]. closing the patient's mouth. To confirm the correct de-

termination of the interalveolar height, we use a phonetic test. Due to good fixation of bases with bite ridges, the patient will pronounce sounds clearly and confidently. If there are no errors, then the distance between the rollers when pronouncing sounds will be within 5-6 mm. After determining the interalveolar height, we fix the lower jaw in the position of central occlusion. The use of a solid base ensures reliable fixation of bases with rollers in the oral cavity and prevents their displacement during wide opening of the mouth and its closing during fixation of central occlusion. When checking the design of artificial teeth, the wax base deforms and falls under the temperature of the oral cavity. Using a solid base with artificial teeth at this stage, we provide active movements of the jaw and masticatory muscles, and this allows us to qualitatively check the occlusal contact. make their correction. In addition, it is possible to carry out language tests, phonetic training at this stage of prosthetics in conditions close to natural.

Conclusion: helps to prevent errors in the preparation of occlusal ridges, determining the intercellular height and fixing the central ratio of the jaws and improve the quality of treatment of the complete absence of teeth with these structures.

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